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Numerical Investigation on Mechanical Properties of Polymer Composites Reinforced with MXene Nanosheets

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Motivation, Aim, Method

- A new class of 2D nanomaterials MXenes was discovered recently. The possibilities of this material as a filler for nano-engineered structural polymer composites have not been studied yet.
- The aim is to identify a suitable finite element methodology for the prediction of mechanical properties of polymer composite reinforced with new MXene 2D nanoparticles.

Mechanical Behaviour of Epoxy/MXene Composite

- The model calibration was performed with Epoxy/MXene experimental tests.
- The strength properties of the interphase layer after an inverse modelling were assumed to be the same as the matrix.
- The model with aligned multilayered MXenes showed higher strength and elastic properties than random one.
- The higher volume fraction and aspect ratio of aligned multilayered MXenes significantly increases Young modulus and strength of the nanocomposite.

Stress in Epoxy/Mxene 3D RVEs: (a) 10 wt% random; (b) 30 wt% aligned

MXene volume fraction, orientation and aspect ratio AR influence on the stress – strain relationship of Epoxy/MXene nanocomposite